

PROPERTY RIGHTS ON THE MOON AND OTHER CELESTIAL BODIES – A CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The moon and other celestial bodies "are not subject to national appropriation by claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means," the Outer Space Treaty states in Chapter A, Article II.

The Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, or the Outer Space Treaty, was ratified and put into effect in 1967. The United Kingdom, the Russian Federation, and the United States of America were the only nations to initially signed this pact. In 1979, the General Assembly voted to approve the Moon Agreement, a much comprehensive convention by non-spacefaring countries that failed to receive enough support. Everything that occurs in space is governed by indefinite laws, including the rules governing property ownership not just in space but also on Earth.

It was 10:29 in the evening of October 4, 1957 in Moscow, when the former Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (U. S. S. R.) launched Sputnik, an artificial satellite that was the first to orbit the earth. It became the advent of humanity's venture into space. Astronauts Neil Armstrong and Buzz Aldrin landed on the moon on July 20, 1969, just eight years after United States of America President John F. Kennedy famously said these words in Congress, "I believe this nation should commit itself to achieving the goal, before this decade is out, of landing a man on the moon and returning him safely to earth." It was one of the most historic events in human history. Most got

inspired. Today, entrepreneurs like Elon Musk and Jeff Bezos have formed space exploration companies that have plans to build on Mars and our moon to advance human civilization. On the government side, after almost fifty (50) years, the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) launched back to the moon on November 16, 2022, through Artemis I, with a goal of staying there in the following missions of the Artemis Program. These developments and efforts would lead us to ask, “Who owns the moon and Mars and the things that will be established on them?”

There is no single legal document that governs everything that happens in space, especially how you can own or build property. Nations made treaties and conventions that are years old to ensure the harmonious facilitation of space-related activities. The Outer Space Treaty, also known by its lengthy name, “Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies,” was signed and enforced in 1967. This treaty was initially signed by three governments: the Russian Federation, the United Kingdom, and the United States of America. Chapter A, Article II, of the Outer Space Treaty says that the moon and other celestial bodies “are not subject to national appropriation by claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means.” What it does not cover are clear boundaries for how the moon and other celestial bodies could be developed and should be used. This leads us to an argument also made by University of Nebraska Space Law Professor and Director of Black Holes Frans von der Dunk that private companies could enjoy the freedom being enjoyed by the states, which means that whatever they do on the moon, their respective countries and governments will be accountable. Professor von der Dunk also mentioned in his interview with Talks On Law that the moon and other celestial bodies cannot be carved and claimed by any country. This means that everyone can exploit the mineral resources that can be found.

If we will treat this treaty like every international law, most especially the “United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea,” or simply known as the “Law of the Sea” or UNCLOS, which was signed in 1982, we can say that countries could clearly and openly violate it on the basis of what happened on December 15, 2016 in the Philippine Exclusive Economic Zone (PEEZ) when China seized an underwater drone from the United States ship USNS Bowditch. Both parties have different claims. China said that it was confiscated due to a potential risk to navigational safety, while the United States disagreed, saying that it was lawful and just collecting scientific data. This incident is an example of an unclear and unspecified global legal construct pertaining to the subject of territory. In another similar example, back in 2016, the Arbitral Tribunal removed China’s “nine dash line” claim, which agrees to the provisions of Part XV of UNCLOS. Even though the Tribunal confirmed the violations made by China, they are still present and still developing (sometimes even harassing Filipino fishermen) in some areas that are internationally agreed to

be part of the Philippines. If these “on earth” conventions can be disregarded by other countries, it is also fair to consider that the vague structure of the Outer Space Treaty (which is considered supreme among all related agreements) can also cause disarray within the international space community and in the global order in general.

We can dig deeper by looking at a more specific agreement called the “Moon Agreement” or the “Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies,” which according to Rand Simberg in his 2012 article for The New Atlantis is a “failed piece of international law.” The Moon Agreement was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1979 and was signed by non-spacefaring countries. This provided a refinement to some of what the Outer Space Treaty already purveyed, but with one major concern: major spacefaring players did not participate. This also clearly portrays that it is not heavily supported. The Moon Agreement was considered by many as a failure but a great lesson from which everyone can learn. The Moon Agreement used “common heritage of mankind” instead of “province of all mankind,” which is being used by the Outer Space Treaty. This simple choice of words became debatable on the grounds of the possibility of needing to establish a separate international entity to organize and distribute resources provided by countries. This can be seen as a possible cause of a “free rider problem,” which is a term for a burdened and problematic result due to overuse caused by fair ownership regardless of what one has contributed. An example of a free rider problem could be the wearing out of government-funded infrastructure because it was used by the public for free.

Embracing this reasoning, we can say that this could be a legitimate concern for those spacefaring nations and explain why they did not support the Moon Agreement. If, for example, Japan built a factory of some kind on the moon, everyone could use it even without providing the initial investments required for it. This dilemma can be solved by establishing a well-drafted International Cooperation Agreement (ICA) that contains the Internal Rules and Regulations (IRR) on how to conduct business and use properties established on the moon and other celestial bodies. This is easier said than done. Even if it was suggested by the Carter Administration that the United States should sign the Moon Treaty, President Ronald Reagan was against this idea because he believed that this was a possible free rider set at the expense of the United States, and he also criticized the Law of the Sea (which is also mentioned above) as a possible way of redistributing influence, power, and most importantly, wealth. He also found little credence in the Moon Treaty, stating that it “distorted” the definition of “common heritage of humankind.”

International law also has no clear definition of “property,” since it has been considered only a passive provision and a protocol to secure agreements that gives additional tools for verification. But we can take a look at the already available codes to understand “property” and its coverage,

such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966, which did not include coherent rights to private property, or the European Convention on Human Rights, which provides some protection against seizure of property. This lack of foundational knowledge and guidelines on what is property under international law should be one of the starting points in the discussion of how properties should be managed on the moon and other celestial bodies. If we have not formulated and adopted a universal concept of property, we could potentially fail to govern possessions beyond Earth.

Properties in space do not just refer to establishments, infrastructures, and machineries but also to the abundant mineral resources present. Mining is a lucrative business; what more if you do it on an asteroid, another planet, or the moon? If a private company from Germany is able to extract precious metals from an asteroid, the legal rights to claim a specific portion of the celestial body and to trade the mined resources can be a painful and problematic process since property rights, even though they are the reason for many people's riches, are still abstract and not in their final form. Mining fundamental assets for production and its lone economic value could be one of the causes of international disputes related to space access in the future.

There are some organizations like the Lunar Embassy, Lunar Registry, Lunar Society, and Lunar Republic that sell parcels of the moon and claim that the documents they provide are legal and authentic. The Lunar Registry's "Registered Claim and Deed for Lunar Property" certificates say that customer properties on the moon are registered at "The Lunar Registry" in New York City, United States of America. It must be safe to question the legality of these transactions, considering that there is no government that owns the moon and the Moon Treaty is not well acknowledged. It is also fine to think that it could be a legal claim since everyone could go to the moon and start a colony. Looking at Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty, it says that "non-governmental entities in outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies, shall require authorization and continuing supervision by the appropriate State Party to the Treaty." This means that the organizations mentioned above did not violate any international law, given that they remain accountable to their governments. If the Lunar Registry is in New York City, the firm is accountable to its state and country. Since the Outer Space Treaty did not clearly state the treatment of private ownership, many extracted something from this flaw. If multiple firms with different owners and clients have similar claims over similar purchases and filings in the future, who will be held liable and how will it be addressed? Can a state like New York facilitate rightful arbitration and just legal proceedings? How will it be managed if competing parties belong to different states or countries? Will the result of any adjudication be an internationally accepted user story that will act as a common interpretation of currently established accords? These are the questions that will be left hanging as of this writing and for which we cannot presume answers.

The space law has not been revised or replaced since 1967, but on November 1, 2022, the United Nations approved a resolution to fabricate a working group that will review current and future threats to space operations, acceptable behavior in space, and formulate new legal instruments. It is timely considering that the existing treaties were negotiated when there were just two (2) spacefaring nations, the U.S.A. and the U.S.S.R. Specific regulations on properties are still uncertain. It is somehow good to present to the table the case of building a well-defined system on how properties should be globally defined on earthly terms and how they should be managed, governed, and acted for before legitimizing the moon and other heavenly bodies as a common settlement for all, which could possibly result in a vaguely drafted pact. As of this moment, we can say that space law has gray areas that are yet to be refined to promote a more inclusive and formative society and industry. Also, participation among non-spacefaring countries must be encouraged, especially as their properties are the most impacted by climate change, which is also one of the driving forces behind why we go to space.

It can be perceived by almost everyone that we are in a new space age. This time we want to build and develop outside our planet and stay for longer periods of time. Countries that were once non-spacefaring are putting in efforts to contribute to the advancement of space. Other enterprises, institutions, and non-governmental organizations around the world are sharing this mission of going to space. Some are taking simpler paths, and some would like to terraform Mars. Whatever the goal is, our collective need for a regulatory framework is here because it will serve as a clear pathway to make everything that we do more sustainable and impactful, not just for us but for the future settlers of space.

Space is already a lawful place, but it still requires more in-depth workings to achieve maturity and clarity. Without proper structure, it can further lead to chaos and precariousness. The formation of a multi-stakeholder committee from different countries would create diversity in perspectives, and more needs could be addressed by tailor-fit solutions, which might help the human race not just in occupying the moon and Mars but also in becoming a multi-planetary species in the future. Like any other aspect of modernization, our collective efforts as citizens of this world will never end, for we shall grow and propel as a civilization, whether it be on earth or outside its premises, so that we can make the moon, Mars, and the rest of space the province of all mankind.

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